

Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan into Low-Carbon Economy Modelling using OSeMOSYS.

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Executive Summary

Nigeria has struggled with unreliable electricity supply despite its rich energy resources. Grid failures and blackouts have been a common occurrence, underscoring the need for sustainable solutions like nuclear power plants and more renewable energy sources. This report provides an assessment of Nigeria's progress towards a low-carbon economy, with a focus on enhancing electricity generation and decreasing CO₂ emissions. To achieve these objectives, the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) was used to evaluate three different scenarios: Business As Usual (BAU), 36% Renewable Energy Source Integration Scenario (RE36) by 2030, and Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) deployment by 2050. The primary goals of these scenarios are to increase electricity generation and access using renewable energy sources and further reduce emissions by integrating nuclear power plants. However, the integration of renewable energy sources and nuclear power generation, as demonstrated in the second and third scenarios, helped to address the challenges of insufficient power generation and reduce CO₂ emissions. The incorporation of 36% renewable energy sources and the inclusion of nuclear power plants in the second and third scenarios showcase the benefits of transitioning to an eco-friendlier energy mix and expanding the installed capacity to satisfy the growing demand for electricity in Nigeria. To achieve cost-effectiveness, it would be prudent for Nigeria to allocate a greater proportion of its investment towards nuclear power plants, as this would likely require less funding than renewable technologies.

1. Introduction

The issue of global warming and its associated consequences has become increasingly prominent on a global scale. This is evidenced by the recording of high atmospheric temperatures, wildfires, flooding, desertification, and a loss of biodiversity around the world (IPPC). To mitigate the effects of climate change and achieve net zero emissions by 2060, a few measures and resolutions have been implemented by global leaders and industries. At the recent COP28 conference, some of the key outcomes included a commitment to triple renewable energy capacity and double current energy efficiency by 2030 (United Nations Framework on Climate Change, 2023). Nigeria has a plan to achieve net zero emissions by 2060 and has also passed its Climate Change Act into law in 2021 (IPPC).

In Nigeria, the energy mix consists of 21% from renewable energy (solar, wind, biomass), 61% from fossil fuels, and 18% from hydro (IRENA). The necessity for increased electricity supply and enhanced grid reliability and security is apparent in Nigeria. However, one of the major challenges facing Nigeria is access to electricity. The centralized electricity grid in Nigeria is mainly powered by fossil fuels with 25 gas-fired thermal stations and 3 hydroelectric power stations (Adebulu, 2021). The 28 electricity generation stations have a total installed capacity of approximately 14,000 MW, but less than 5,000 MW is transmitted to a large portion of the population of over 206 million people (USAID, 2022). This puts Nigeria among the countries with the least access to electricity in sub-Saharan Africa and globally. Therefore, this report aims to evaluate Nigeria's energy transition and efforts to increase electricity access with a net zero target in mind.

Purpose and Scope

The utilisation of renewable energy sources is one of the methods for increasing access to electricity, as per the findings of the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) in 2018 on accelerating SDG 7. In accordance with Nigeria's energy transition plan, this approach can help reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, enhance electricity generation, and improve access to achieve net zero by 2060. The report's scope is limited to the period between 2015 and 2050, and its aim is to increase electricity access for approximately 41% of Nigeria's unelectrified population (Tracking SDG7, 2023). The purpose of this report is to devise a model for the Nigerian energy transition pathway with the aim of accomplishing the following objectives: Firstly, to increase

electricity generation by incorporating 36% share of renewable energy sources into the main grid, secondly, to significantly reduce the level of CO₂ emissions by implementing nuclear power generation and finally, to propose suitable electricity generation sources that can facilitate Nigeria's energy transition plan by the year 2060.

The research questions that guide this analysis are: How can the integration of renewable energy sources affect the Nigeria electricity mix? How will the implementation of the nuclear power plant contribute to reducing emission levels?

2. Methodology

The OSeMOSYS energy modelling tool is utilised for extended capacity expansion planning in this study. OSeMOSYS is a bottom-up optimisation energy modelling system that offers a comprehensive representation of technologies and flows within the energy system. OSeMOSYS is used to develop long-term analyses of the energy sector at a range of scales, electrification pathways to understanding the environmental and economic implication of decarbonisation scenarios (Canone et al 2024).

It considers various aspects such as efficiency, expenses, resource utilisation, and environmental impacts. In line with other long-term optimisation models, OSeMOSYS operates under the assumption of perfect foresight and perfect competition in energy markets, implying a thorough understanding of future circumstances and the operation of energy markets in a perfectly competitive manner. It operates as a deterministic and linear optimisation framework. Its adaptability has led to extensive utilisation as a long-term optimisation model across several countries (Canone et al., 2023). The data used in this report includes details on energy consumption, production, supply capacity among other relevant details. To construct long-term energy transition scenarios in the Nigerian context, the OSeMOSYS modelling tool is employed in this study.

The modelling assumptions made for the integration of 36% renewable energy sources (RE36%) in the second scenario included maintaining investment in natural gas power plants while increasing the renewable energy share to 36% by 2030. Additionally, for the Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) scenario it was assumed that the generation from natural gas power plants would decrease when the nuclear power plant was installed to reduce the CO₂ emissions.

As shown in Figure 1, three scenarios were modelled as described.

1. The "business as usual" scenario involves maintaining the historical and current trend without any intervention from government policies. In this scenario, power generation in Nigeria will primarily be fueled by natural gas and hydro, and the percentage of access to electricity and the absence of emissions reduction targets based on the historical trend and the installed capacity of various technologies will all remain constant.
2. The Renewable Energy Integration (RE36%) Scenario assesses the potential of the country to fulfil its energy needs by 2030 while simultaneously reducing emissions by increasing the percentage of renewable energy in the national grid to 36%, as outlined in the policy statement of 2021 (REMP, 2021).
3. Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) Integration into the grid mix. The integration of nuclear power plants (NPPs) into the grid is evaluated to determine their potential for lowering emission levels. In this scenario, a 4000 MW nuclear power plant installation and a reduction in natural gas capacity are considered.

Figure 1: Presentation of the 3 modelled scenarios.

3. Results and Discussions

The chart depicted in Figure 2 illustrates the intended capacity expansion plan for power generation in terms of PJ from various energy technologies between 2020 and 2050. The RE36 and NPP scenarios demonstrate a more diversified energy supply mix, indicating a shift towards more resilient and sustainable energy sources compared to the BAU scenario, which heavily relies on natural gas.

The total power generation from natural gas power plants under the BAU scenario is anticipated to reach 2400PJ in 2050, which is about 4.8 more than the 500PJ generated in 2030. The power generation in the RE36 and NPP scenarios increases slightly, with a total generation of 50 PJ each in 2050. The RE36 and NPP scenarios are expected to produce more power, thereby increasing the electrification rate to meet all sectors' energy demands.

Without policy formulation, natural gas would be the predominant energy source in Nigeria's energy sector, constituting nearly 70% of the power generation in 2070. However, the transition towards clean energy sources is being considered through the incorporation of solar photovoltaic (PV), onshore wind and other renewables in the RE36 scenarios. The power generation from the natural gas power plant accounts for approximately 36% in the RE36 and 44% in the NPP scenarios in 2040. Moreover, the integration of nuclear power plants becomes noticeable by 2040 in the NPP scenario.

Figure 2: Power Generation (PJ) Chart for Nigeria's three Scenarios

Figure 3 exhibits the installed capacities for all the technologies across the three scenarios. The RE36 scenario demonstrates an elevated share of renewable energy from the previous 21% to a 36% share in the installed capacity, compared to the BAU scenario. The NPP scenario signifies a further reduction in the installed capacity of natural gas power plants and the integration of nuclear power plants into the grid mix. By 2070, under the BAU scenario, the total installed capacity is estimated to be approximately 150 GW, whereas it rises to around 270 GW in the same year under the RE36 scenario. In comparison, the NPP scenario has a capacity of roughly 260GW. This increase in capacity is significantly attributable to the integration of renewable energy (RE) technologies. Additionally, both the RE36 and NPP scenarios contribute to higher electrification rates. In these scenarios, natural gas (NG) is incorporated as a mix with RE36 resources and nuclear power due to its higher capacity factor.

Figure 3: Installed Capacity for Nigeria's three Scenarios

Figure 4 displays the discounted cost for all three scenarios. According to the estimates, the BAU scenario's Nigeria needs to invest around \$USD 460 Billion, while for the RE36 scenario's it is estimated at \$USD 432 Billion. Conversely, the NPP scenario estimate is roughly \$USD 429 Billion. Moreover, under the NPP scenario, with higher power generation from nuclear power plants, the cost reduction was even more significant, amounting to approximately \$USD 31.27billion in comparison with the BAU. This suggests that in Nigeria, investing in nuclear power technologies may prove to be more advantageous than relying on intermittent renewables.

Figure 4: Total discounted cost for the three Scenarios.

The accompanying Figure 5 presents the overall CO₂ emissions across various situations from 2020 to 2050. In the BAU scenario, the prevailing trends in the energy sector are responsible for a significant increase in annual emissions, reaching approximately 240 MtCO₂ in 2050. However, the emissions are slightly lower under the RE36 scenario with 160 MtCO₂, and the NPP scenarios have roughly 145 MtCO₂. The RE36 and NPP scenarios have demonstrated a considerable reduction of 80 MtCO₂ for RE36 and approximately 96 MtCO₂ for the NPP in 2070 compared to the BAU scenario. These outcomes indicate that diversifying the energy mix and incorporating clean and sustainable energy solutions can decrease overall emissions, which in turn can assist in achieving Nigeria's targets. Furthermore, additional effort is required to achieve net zero emissions in Nigeria, including the implementation of new policy and regulatory frameworks.

Figure 5: Annual carbon dioxide emissions for the three scenarios

The outcomes of these findings indicate that Nigeria possesses considerable potential for renewable energy sources, with a more affordable cost compared to the prevailing trend. Furthermore, transitioning to clean energy sources in the national grid will boost Nigeria's capacity, thereby increasing the power available for transmission to meet the growing energy demand in the country. This shift is primarily characterized by an increase in renewable energy installation capacity and a slight decrease in natural gas usage, which results in a reduction of CO₂ emissions from the country. Worth noting is the significant impact of the installation of a 4000 MW Nuclear power plant in reducing the nation's CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, it is crucial to emphasize that the implications of these results depend on the necessity of implementing strategic planning and investing in renewable energy infrastructure in order to achieve these future energy scenarios. These findings hold relevance for decision-makers and stakeholders within the energy sector, as they can be utilized to create policies that encourage the development of clean energy technologies, thereby supporting Nigeria's transition goals.

In the immediate future, it is essential that Nigeria increases its investment in renewable energy sources to make a successful transition and fulfil its commitments to COP29. Furthermore, a plan for constructing large-scale nuclear power plants must be put in place to significantly decrease carbon emissions in the power sector, a feat that will require substantial investment in nuclear energy. It is crucial that the necessary funds be allocated towards achieving this long-term goal. Moreover, future research could explore the potential cost-effectiveness of biomass and geothermal energy, as well as the possibility of increasing electricity access to 90% of Nigeria's population through FlexTool modelling.

5. Conclusion

The available electricity capacity and power production in Nigeria suggest a state of inadequacy in meeting the power needs of over 206 million people. However, the integration of renewable energy sources and nuclear power generation, as demonstrated in the second and third scenarios, helped to address the challenges of insufficient power generation and reduce CO₂ emissions. This aligns with Nigeria's energy transition plan to attain net zero emissions by 2060. The incorporation of 36% renewable energy sources and the inclusion of nuclear power plants in the second and third scenarios showcase the benefits of transitioning to an eco-friendlier energy mix and expanding the installed capacity to satisfy the growing demand for electricity in Nigeria. The decrease in carbon dioxide emissions confirms that the increase in renewable energy sources has a positive effect on the environment, as anticipated in the net zero era. To achieve cost-effectiveness, it would be prudent for Nigeria to allocate a greater proportion of its investment towards nuclear power plants, as this would likely require less funding than renewable technologies.

The integration of additional renewable energy sources into the central grid system will augment electricity power generation and diminish the scarcity of access. The expenditure on constructing nuclear power plants will augment power generation and further minimize emissions, thereby facilitating the attainment of net zero status by the year 2060. Additional power generation can be produced from nuclear energy sources beyond 2050.

REFERENCES

Adebulu, T. 2021. *Premium Times: Why Nigeria's power sector suffers low gas supply despite having Africa's largest gas reserve*. Accessed 03 March 2024 <[ANALYSIS: Why Nigeria's power sector suffers low gas supply despite having Africa's largest reserve](#)>

Cannone C, Allington L, de Wet N, Shivakumar A, Goyns P, Valderrama C, Kell A, Plazas Niño FA, Mohanty R, Kapor V, et al. clicSAND for OSeMOSYS: A User-Friendly Interface Using Open-Source Optimisation Software for Energy System Modelling Analysis. *Energies*. 2024; 17(16):3923. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17163923>

IRENA,2023. *Tracking SDG7: The energy progress report 2023*. Accessed 14 August, 2024,<[Tracking SDG7: The energy progress report 2023](#)>

IPPC, AR6 Synthesis report: Climate change, *Intergovernmental panel on climate change*. Accessed 20 August 2024 <<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/>>

Tracking SDG7, 2023. *The energy progress report*. Sustainable development goals 7 joint report, Thee energy progress report website Accessed 20 August 2024,< [Downloads | Tracking SDG 7](#)>

REMP target, IEA:accessed 20 August 2024< [Nigeria Renewable Energy Master Plan – Policies - IEA](#)>